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[Factors Influencing the Attitude of Information Professionals Toward Digital Preservation at Riphah International University]

Sami Ullah

Crop Reporter, Crop Reporting Services (Agriculture Department).

Email: samiullah0203@gmail.com. ORCID: [0009-0000-0287-0198](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0287-0198)

Adil Ahmad

Librarian, School of Health Science, Peshawar

Dr. Sajjad Ahmad*

Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Peshawar. Corresponding Author Email: sajjad_lis74@yahoo.com

Kalim Ullah

Information Officer, Information Services Department, Riphah International University, Malakand Campus.

Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the factors influencing the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation at Riphah International University. A quantitative research design was employed, guided by previous empirical studies on digital preservation practices in academic libraries. The target population consisted of 51 library professionals across Riphah International University and its sub-campuses, from which 47 valid responses were obtained (92.2% response rate). Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering four constructs: technological awareness, professional training, institutional support, and attitude toward digital preservation, measured on a five-point Likert scale. Reliability analysis confirmed strong internal consistency across all constructs ($\alpha = 0.954$). Descriptive, correlation, and regression analyses were conducted using SPSS. The results revealed that technological awareness ($\beta = .802, p < .001$), institutional support ($\beta = .773, p < .001$), and professional training ($\beta = .778, p < .001$) significantly and positively influenced the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation. Among these predictors, technological awareness exhibited the strongest effect, explaining 64% of the variance in attitudes. The findings underscore the importance of improving technical competencies, institutional infrastructure, and continuous professional development to enhance digital preservation practices. It is recommended that the university strengthen policy frameworks, provide adequate financial and technical support, and promote ongoing capacity-building initiatives to sustain effective digital preservation efforts.

Keywords: Digital Preservation, Technological Awareness, Institutional Support, Professional Training, Information Professionals, Riphah International University.

Background of the Study

Digital preservation refers to the long-term maintenance and protection of digital materials, including both “born-digital” resources, those created originally in digital form, and digitized materials converted from physical formats, such as print documents, photographs, and artifacts (Arora, 2009). According to the Society of American Archivists, preservation is the professional responsibility of safeguarding materials against chemical, mechanical, and physical deterioration to extend their usability and protect them from harm or loss (Segaetsho & Moloji, 2019).

The preservation and management of digital records is a complex process involving technical, administrative, organizational, and policy-related issues. However, a strong technical foundation remains essential, particularly since digital content must be preserved in a form that can be migrated and copied unchanged as storage technologies evolve (Rothenberg, 1999; Holdsworth, 2006).

Historically, the concept of digital preservation has developed alongside advances in information technologies. In India, for example, libraries in the mid-1980s created in-house databases and used electronic resources stored on floppy disks, which later became obsolete and were replaced by CD-ROMs and DVDs (Arora, 2009). Similarly, many national institutions across the globe initiated digital preservation programs: the

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U.S. Library of Congress launched the National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program, the National Library of Australia pursued preservation initiatives under ICABS, and the Netherlands developed the Digital Information Archiving System (DIAS) (Samiei, 2020). In Iran, the National Library and Archives of Iran began digitization projects in 2001, culminating in the creation of the “Digital National Library” by 2008 to preserve rare materials for long-term access (Samiei, 2020).

The significance of digital preservation lies in its role in reducing risks of information loss due to bit rot, obsolescence, or other vulnerabilities. While preservation strategies cannot guarantee absolute security, they help ensure that valuable digital resources remain accessible over time (Wilson, 2017; Quisbert et al., 2009). Libraries, in particular, are viewed by the academic community as custodians of digital collections, tasked with preserving materials that were once accessible, whether acquired through subscriptions, purchased in digital media, or digitized in-house (Arora, 2009). However, long-term preservation remains a challenge due to the short lifespans of media, hardware and software obsolescence, and unstable online resources (Chen, 2001).

Scholars have emphasized the need for effective digital preservation strategies. Preservation requires not only safeguarding digital records but also documenting and adapting to changes in preservation infrastructures and policies (Moore, 2008). Strategies include technology preservation, migration, emulation, encapsulation, back-up systems, use of identifiers, and even “digital archaeology,” which attempts to recover inaccessible resources due to technological obsolescence (Samiei, 2020). Selecting what should be preserved is also essential, requiring identification, characterization, and description of digital objects to ensure long-term usability (Becker et al., 2009; Kastellec, 2012).

Despite its importance, digital preservation faces numerous problems, such as the lack of proven long-term methods, fragility of storage media, and the absence of sustainable tools to manage rapid technological change (Ruusalepp, 2005; Gladney, 2007; Gatenby, 2004). Bishoff and Smith (2015) further highlighted barriers such as lack of funding, expertise, and institutional support, while Corrado and Moulaison (2014) and the Council of Canadian Academies (2015) emphasized that sustainability requires proper allocation of resources, policy frameworks, collaboration, and technical expertise. In the Pakistani context, studies have shown that librarians’ attitudes toward the use of information technology in preservation are shaped by factors such as computer literacy, training, frequency of technology use, and institutional infrastructure (Asif & Ahmad, 2021).

The study aims to highlight the role of technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training in shaping the attitudes of information professionals toward digital preservation. Because, in the Pakistani context, particularly at Riphah International University and its sub-campuses, little is known about how these factors influence information professionals’ attitudes. This gap in knowledge poses a challenge for implementing sustainable preservation practices in libraries of Riphah International University and its sub-campuses. Without such understanding, these institutions may struggle to safeguard valuable digital resources effectively. Therefore, investigating

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these factors is essential to ensure long-term access and preservation of digital content.

Statement of the Problem

Digital preservation is often discussed alongside related terms such as digital curation, archiving, and stewardship, and encompasses processes that stabilize and protect authentic digital records (Drijfhout, 2007; Segaletsho & Moloji, 2019). It involves both born-digital resources and digital surrogates created from print formats (Noonan, 2014). Despite its growing importance in academic institutions, the success of digital preservation largely depends on the attitudes of information professionals. Factors such as technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training have been identified as critical in shaping these attitudes (Asif & Ahmad, 2021). However, limited empirical evidence exists on how these factors influence professionals in the Pakistani context. At Riphah International University and its sub-campuses, information professionals are exercising digital preservation practices, but the various factors affecting their attitudes are not yet studied; this gap hinders the development of sustainable preservation strategies. Therefore, it is necessary to examine the extent to which these factors contribute to fostering positive attitudes toward digital preservation.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of technological awareness on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation?
2. What is the role of institutional support in shaping the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation?
3. What is the effect of professional training on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation?

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

According to the theory of planned behavior, human behavior is guided by three kinds of considerations: beliefs about the likely consequences of the behavior (*behavioral beliefs*), beliefs about the normative expectations of others (*normative beliefs*), and beliefs about the presence of factors that may facilitate or impede performance of the behavior (*control beliefs*). In their respective aggregates, behavioral beliefs produce a favorable or unfavorable attitude toward the behavior; normative beliefs result in perceived social pressure or subjective norm; and control beliefs give rise to perceived behavioral control or self-efficacy. The effects of attitude toward the behavior and subjective norm on intention are moderated by perception of behavioral control (Bosnjak et al., 2020). The theory of planned behavior is a widely applied expectancy-value model of attitude-behavior relationships, which has met with some degree of success in predicting a variety of behaviors (Ajzen, 1988). The TPB attempts to also predict nonvolitional behaviors by incorporating perceptions of control over performance of the behavior as an additional predictor (Ajzen, 1988).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Research Hypotheses

Based on the above conceptual framework, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H1: Technological awareness has a positive influence on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.

H2: Institutional support has a positive effect on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.

H3: Professional training has a positive effect on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.

Literature Review

Digital preservation has emerged as a critical concern for academic libraries worldwide, given the challenges of technological obsolescence, unstable storage media, and institutional constraints. Several studies have explored sustainability, practices, challenges, and the role of information professionals in ensuring long-term access to digital resources. This review synthesizes existing scholarship on digital preservation with emphasis on technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training, as these directly relate to the present study.

Masenyana and Ngulube (2020) conducted a survey across 27 South African academic institutions, achieving an impressive response rate of 81.5%. Their findings revealed that institutional support (95.5%), copyright and intellectual property rights (100%), and technical expertise (95.5%) were the most influential factors sustaining digital preservation. Enabling conditions such as management support (100%), effective leadership (95.5%), and adequate training (95.4%) further enhanced preservation outcomes. The researchers developed a conceptual integrated model that organized sustainability factors into management, resource, and technology dimensions, aligned with established frameworks such as OAIS and the PSR Troika model. Their study demonstrates that sustainable digital preservation requires not only technological infrastructure but also organizational commitment and skilled human resources.

Abubakar et al. (2024) examined preservation practices among 315 library staff in Niger State. Results showed an overall mean score of 2.87 (SD = 0.908), with disaster preparedness ranking highest (M = 2.99) and digital preservation lowest (M = 2.76). Attitudes toward preservation were generally positive (M = 3.24, SD = 0.686), though

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challenges such as neglect and insufficient resources persisted. The demographic profile indicated that most respondents were male (63.5%) and degree holders (51.4%), suggesting qualified personnel but with limited support. The authors concluded that positive staff attitudes must be reinforced with institutional resources, training, and policies to strengthen preservation capacity.

Akintonde and Awujoola (2022) surveyed 262 library personnel across nine university libraries in Southwest Nigeria to examine the role of ICT skills in digital preservation practices. Staff demonstrated strong skills in word processing ($M = 3.56$, $SD = 0.598$), printing ($M = 3.52$, $SD = 0.572$), and internet navigation ($M = 3.56$, $SD = 0.523$), but weaker skills in web page creation ($M = 2.89$, $SD = 0.782$). Preservation practices included theft security ($M = 3.37$, $SD = 0.661$), lamination/photocopying ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 0.673$), and book binding ($M = 3.31$, $SD = 0.744$). Correlation analysis revealed weak but significant positive relationships between ICT skills and digital preservation, with computing application skills showing the strongest link ($r = 0.424$, $p < 0.05$). However, financial limitations ($M = 3.18$, $SD = 0.790$), erratic power supply ($M = 2.84$, $SD = 0.896$), and lack of preservation policy ($M = 2.55$, $SD = 0.841$) emerged as barriers. This study highlights the importance of continuous ICT training for librarians to enhance digital preservation practices.

Sambo et al. (2017) investigated challenges of digital preservation through a survey of 172 librarians at a national conference in Nigeria. Although all respondents (100%) recognized digital preservation challenges, 83% lacked relevant training, 78% reported absence of backup standards, and 66% had never received any digital preservation training. Common barriers included inadequate funding, obsolete hardware/software, and absence of institutional strategies. The study recommended increased training (31%) and improved funding (24%) to address these limitations. Similarly, Sambo (2014) surveyed 300 Nigerian librarians, reporting that 70% had not received preservation training, and 59% stated their libraries lacked policies. Only 28% of respondents were familiar with technology preservation, while the majority cited training, funding, and policy gaps as major challenges. These studies collectively underline that inadequate institutional support and lack of professional development are persistent issues in sustaining digital preservation.

Maron (2008) conducted a web-based survey of 1,371 U.S. academic library directors, receiving a 13.6% response rate. Findings showed that while over 80% agreed on the importance of preserving e-journals, only 34% reported active participation in preservation initiatives such as LOCKSS or Portico. Institutional size, budget, and research orientation influenced engagement, while smaller institutions often assumed larger ones would take responsibility. The study concluded that clearer definitions, shared responsibilities, and stronger collaboration are needed to bridge the gap between awareness and practice. Similarly, Gracy and Kahn (2011), through a literature review, categorized preservation research into digital preservation and curation, mass digitization, risk management, preservation education, and the shift from print to digital. They emphasized that academic libraries are moving from custodial roles to more proactive digital content management, requiring leadership, evolving standards, and

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enhanced professional skills.

Kastellec (2012) explored practical limitations in digital preservation, emphasizing cost as the most pervasive constraint. While technological challenges such as storage and redundancy have been partially addressed, non-technical issues, particularly access, legal restrictions, and funding, remain major obstacles. Kastellec argued that preservation must often function as triage, where institutions prioritize only a fraction of digital content for long-term storage. This study suggests that financial and institutional realities significantly influence the scope of preservation efforts, supporting the argument that institutional support and policy development are critical.

The reviewed literature highlights recurring themes: technological awareness and ICT skills are crucial but unevenly developed across contexts (Akintonde & Awujoola, 2022); institutional support in the form of funding, policies, and leadership is a consistent enabler of sustainable preservation (Masenya & Ngulube, 2020; Abubakar et al., 2024); and professional training remains inadequate in many academic libraries, hindering effective adoption of preservation practices (Sambo et al., 2017; Sambo, 2014). Studies from Africa, the U.S., and beyond confirm that positive attitudes toward preservation exist among information professionals, but these attitudes are insufficient without institutional backing and resources (Maron, 2008; Gracy & Kahn, 2011). The literature also emphasizes the practical limitations of preservation, particularly cost and policy gaps (Kastellec, 2012).

Despite these contributions, there remains limited empirical research in the Pakistani context. Specifically, little is known about how technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training influence the attitudes of information professionals toward digital preservation in universities such as Riphah International University and its sub-campuses. Addressing this gap is crucial for developing effective strategies to safeguard digital resources and promote the sustainable preservation of academic knowledge.

Methodology

The researchers reviewed the relevant literature on factors influencing information professionals' attitudes toward digital preservation. Researchers relied on a quantitative research design to seek answers to their research questions as most of the previous studies used the same approach (Abubakar et al., 2024; Akintonde & Awujoola, 2022; Khan & Bhatti, 2017).

Population

The total population includes 51 Information Services department's (Libraries) staff, i.e, librarians with designations (Director, Deputy Director, Senior Manager, Manager, Deputy Manager, Assistant Manager, Information Executive, Information Officer, and Assistant Information Officer) working in the Riphah International University including its sub campuses. Other categories of para-professionals (library attendants, bookbinders, library clerks, etc.) were excluded. Thus, the respondents for this study comprised 47 librarians (92.2% response rate).

Data Collection Instrument

The questionnaire for the study was designed to investigate factors influencing the

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attitudes of information professionals toward digital preservation at Riphah International University. Section A focused on demographic variables, including gender, qualification, and designation. Section B measured the technological awareness, professional training, and institutional support, and the attitude toward digital preservation, using a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). Items on technological awareness were adapted from prior studies emphasizing the competencies required for managing and preserving digital objects (Khan & Bhatti, 2017; Ramzan et al., 2021). Professional training constructs were informed by research identifying the influence of structured training programs, workshops, and seminars on enhancing skills and engagement in digital preservation (Sambo et al., 2017; Sambo et al., 2014). Institutional support items were based on literature stressing the role of policies, funding, backup practices, and organizational commitment in sustaining preservation initiatives (Masenya & Ngulube, 2020; Abubakar et al., 2024). Finally, attitude toward digital preservation was operationalized using established scales that conceptualize attitude as an individual's perception and readiness to act, highlighting its significance in the success of preservation strategies (Fati et al., 2024).

Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire was shared on the email distribution group and also in personal WhatsApp to the librarians' of Riphah International University. The responses of the 47 participants were coded in Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) for further analysis.

Measure(s)

Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used to analyze the data and draw conclusions. Pearson correlation and simple linear regression analyses were conducted to explore the factors influencing information professionals' attitudes toward digital preservation. The data's reliability was assessed with Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis, which evaluates the internal consistency of scale items. As shown in Table 1, Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients for "technological awareness" ($\alpha = 0.898$), "institutional support" ($\alpha = 0.844$), "professional training" ($\alpha = 0.842$), and "attitude toward digital preservation" ($\alpha = 0.877$) were all relatively high, indicating that the items within each construct were positively correlated and internally consistent. The overall reliability of the scale was $\alpha = 0.954$, demonstrating excellent instrument reliability. Cronbach's alpha values between 0.70 and 0.95 are generally regarded as acceptable being highly reliable.

Table 1: Study variables, number of statements/items, and Cronbach's alpha values.

Study variables	No of items	Cronbach's alpha
Technological awareness	7	.898
Institutional support	6	.844
Professional training	6	.842
Attitude toward digital preservation.	5	.877
Composite reliability	24	.954

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents (N = 47) showed that the majority were male (n = 41, 87.2%), while females represented a smaller proportion (n = 6, 12.8%). In

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terms of educational qualifications, most respondents held an MS/M.Phil. degree (n = 30, 63.8%), followed by MLISC/BS (n = 14, 29.8%) and PhD (n = 3, 6.4%). Regarding designation, the largest groups were Information Officers (n = 15, 31.9%) and Information Executives (n = 13, 27.7%). Smaller proportions included Assistant Managers (n = 7, 14.9%), Deputy Managers (n = 5, 10.6%), Senior Managers (n = 3, 6.4%), Assistant Information Officers (n = 2, 4.3%), Managers (n = 1, 2.1%), and Deputy Directors (n = 1, 2.1%).

Table 2: Demographics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	%age
Gender		
Male	41	87.2
Female	6	12.8
Educational Level		
MLISC/BS	14	29.8
MS/M.PHIL	30	63.8
PHD	3	6.4
Designation		
Deputy Director	1	2.1
Senior Manager	3	6.4
Manager	1	2.1
Deputy Manager	5	10.6
Assistant Manager	7	14.9
Information Executive	13	27.7
Information Officer	15	31.9
Assistant Information Officer	2	4.3
Total	47	100.0

Key Findings

RQ1: What is the influence of technological awareness on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation?

Table 3 shows that respondents demonstrated varying levels of technological awareness in relation to their attitude toward digital preservation. The highest mean score was reported for the ability to convert hard copies into electronic copies ($M = 3.81, SD = 1.41$), followed by resolving office software issues independently ($M = 3.79, SD = 1.30$) and understanding how to preserve original application programs ($M = 3.72, SD = 1.16$). The ability to transfer digital materials across platforms also received a relatively high mean ($M = 3.66, SD = 1.45$), while creating original applications to access digital objects on future platforms was rated similarly ($M = 3.64, SD = 1.09$). Lower mean scores were observed for installing new computer hardware or devices ($M = 3.44, SD = 1.27$) and designing and implementing a preservation programme ($M = 3.43, SD = 0.99$). Overall, the results suggest that respondents possessed stronger awareness and skills in basic digital preservation tasks, whereas more advanced technical competencies were comparatively less developed. These findings indicate that higher technological awareness may positively shape the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.

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Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of technological awareness on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation

Statement	Mean	SD
I know how to convert hard copies into electronic copies.	3.81	1.409
I can resolve Office software issues (MS Office, Open Office, etc.) independently.	3.79	1.301
I understand how to preserve original application programs.	3.72	1.155
I can transfer digital materials across computer platforms (e.g., floppy to CD, Word to PDF).	3.66	1.449
I can create original applications to access digital objects on future platforms.	3.64	1.092
I can install new computer hardware or devices for preservation purposes.	3.44	1.271
I can design and implement a preservation program.	3.43	.994

RQ2: What is the role of institutional support in shaping the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation?

Table 4 shows that respondents reported varying perceptions of institutional support in shaping their attitudes toward digital preservation. The highest mean score was observed for the statement that new technologies require sufficient funds for staff training, even at high costs ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 1.08$), suggesting strong agreement on the importance of financial investment in training. Moderate agreement was found for the provision of formal training programs on digital preservation ($M = 3.66$, $SD = 1.32$) and the existence of a clear policy guiding digital preservation practices ($M = 3.60$, $SD = 1.26$). Lower mean scores were reported for institutional funding support for digital preservation activities ($M = 3.33$, $SD = 1.41$), regular backup practices ($M = 3.43$, $SD = 1.50$), and concerns that limited support discourages the acquisition of effective preservation tools ($M = 3.47$, $SD = 1.12$). Overall, these results suggest that while respondents recognized the importance of institutional backing, they perceived gaps in consistent financial, policy, and technical support. These findings provide initial evidence, indicating that institutional support plays a critical role in shaping the attitudes of information professionals toward digital preservation.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of institutional support in shaping the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation

Statement	Mean	SD
New technologies require sufficient funds for staff training, even at high costs.	4.04	1.083

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My institution provides a formal training program on digital preservation.	3.66	1.323
My library has a clear policy guiding digital preservation practices.	3.60	1.262
Limited institutional support discourages my ability to acquire effective digital preservation tools.	3.47	1.120
My library has regular backup practices.	3.43	1.500
My institution provides adequate funds for digital preservation activities.	3.33	1.414

RQ3: What is the effect of professional training on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation?

Table 5 shows that respondents generally acknowledged the effect of professional training on their attitudes toward digital preservation. The highest mean score was reported for the statement that workshops and seminars increase confidence in digital preservation tools ($M = 3.71, SD = 1.29$), highlighting the perceived value of practical, hands-on training opportunities. Similarly, respondents agreed that professional training has improved their overall attitude toward digital preservation ($M = 3.57, SD = 1.36$) and that they receive some form of continuous training ($M = 3.55, SD = 1.28$). However, relatively lower mean scores were observed for limited structured training programs ($M = 3.40, SD = 1.21$) and the discouraging impact of a lack of formal training ($M = 3.40, SD = 1.23$), as well as for the limited institutional sponsorship of professional development programs ($M = 3.51, SD = 1.43$). These findings suggest that while professional training opportunities positively influence attitudes toward digital preservation, gaps remain in the consistency and structure of such programs. Thus, the results provide supportive evidence, emphasizing the critical role of professional training in shaping positive professional attitudes toward digital preservation.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of professional training on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation

Statement	Mean	SD
Workshops and seminars increase my confidence in digital preservation tools.	3.71	1.290
Professional training has improved my attitude toward digital preservation.	3.57	1.363
I get continuous training in digital preservation.	3.55	1.282
My institution rarely organizes or sponsors professional development programs focused on digital preservation.	3.51	1.428
There are limited structured training programs on digital preservation.	3.40	1.210

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Lack of formal training discourages my participation in digital preservation. 3.40 1.228

To address the research questions, which examined the relationship between the three attributes of attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation, the following three hypotheses were formulated:

- H1: Technological awareness has a positive influence on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.
- H2: Institutional support has a positive effect on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.
- H3: Professional training has a positive effect on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.

To answer this question and test the three hypotheses, the researcher conducted two tests: a correlation test to confirm the association between independent variables and outcome variables, and a regression analysis to examine the relationship between the three predictors of information professionals' attitudes toward digital preservation. As shown in the table 6, conducting the Pearson correlation test before testing the three hypotheses is essential. The results of these tests indicated a correlation among the three factors influencing information professionals' attitudes toward digital preservation.

Table 6: Correlation

Constructs	1	2	3	4
Technological Awareness	1			
Institutional Support	.691**	1		
Professional Training	.767**	.758**	1	
Attitude toward Digital Preservation	.802**	.773**	.778**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation matrix in Table 6 shows significant positive relationships among all constructs. The highest correlation is observed between Professional Training and Technological Awareness ($r = .767, p < .01$), reflecting a strong positive association. This suggests that professionals who receive more training are also more technologically aware, which in turn strengthens their engagement with digital preservation practices. Similarly, Attitude toward Digital Preservation is strongly correlated with all three predictors: Technological Awareness ($r = .802, p < .01$), Institutional Support ($r = .773, p < .01$), and Professional Training ($r = .778, p < .01$).

Overall, the correlations among the constructs range from $r = .691$ to $r = .802$, all of which are strong and statistically significant. These findings provide sufficient justification for proceeding with the regression analyses reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Regression Analysis

Statistic	Technology Awareness	Institutional Support	Professional Training
R	.802	.773	.778
R ²	.644	.597	.605

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Adjusted R ²	.636	.587	.596
F-Value	77.775	63.66	65.783
Sig. (F-test)	.000	.000	.000
B (Unstandardized Coefficient)	0.727	0.727	0.715
Std. Error (B)	0.082	0.091	0.088
β (Standardized Beta)	.802	.773	.778
t-value	8.819	7.98	8.111
Sig. (t-test)	0.000	.000	.000
95% Confidence Interval	[0.561, 0.893]	[0.543, 0.910]	[0.537, 0.893]
Results	H1 Supported	H2 Supported	H3 Supported

A series of simple linear regressions was conducted to examine the effects of technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation.

H1, the results indicated that technological awareness was a significant predictor of attitudes toward digital preservation, $R = .80$, $R^2 = .64$, Adjusted $R^2 = .64$, $F(1, 43) = 77.78$, $p < .001$. Technological awareness explained approximately 64% of the variance in attitudes toward digital preservation. The regression coefficient was positive and significant, $B = 0.73$, $SE = 0.08$, $\beta = .80$, $t(43) = 8.82$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.56, 0.89], suggesting that higher technological awareness leads to a more favorable attitude toward digital preservation.

H2, institutional support also significantly predicted attitudes toward digital preservation, $R = .77$, $R^2 = .60$, Adjusted $R^2 = .59$, $F(1, 43) = 63.66$, $p < .001$. Institutional support explained nearly 60% of the variance in attitudes. The coefficient was positive and significant, $B = 0.73$, $SE = 0.09$, $\beta = .77$, $t(43) = 7.98$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.54, 0.91], indicating that greater institutional support is associated with more positive attitudes toward digital preservation.

H3, professional training was also found to be a significant predictor of attitudes toward digital preservation, $R = .78$, $R^2 = .61$, Adjusted $R^2 = .60$, $F(1, 43) = 65.78$, $p < .001$. Professional training accounted for approximately 61% of the variance in attitudes. The coefficient was positive and significant, $B = 0.72$, $SE = 0.09$, $\beta = .78$, $t(43) = 8.11$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.54, 0.89], suggesting that higher levels of professional training enhance positive attitudes toward digital preservation.

The findings demonstrate that technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training each have strong, positive, and statistically significant effects on the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation. Among the three predictors, technological awareness ($\beta = .80$, $R^2 = .64$) exerted the strongest influence.

Discussion

The current study examined the impact of technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training on the attitudes of information professionals toward digital preservation in academic libraries. The findings show that all three factors significantly influence attitudes toward digital preservation, emphasizing the importance of skills,

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resources, and training in encouraging sustainable preservation efforts. Each hypothesis was confirmed, with technological awareness identified as the strongest predictor. These results agree with previous research and provide new empirical evidence from the Pakistani context, where limited studies have been done on this topic.

Technological awareness showed a significant effect on attitudes toward digital preservation, $R = .80$, $R^2 = .64$, $F(1, 43) = 77.78$, $p < .001$. The regression coefficient was positive and statistically significant ($B = 0.73$, $SE = 0.08$, $\beta = .80$, $t(43) = 8.82$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.56, 0.89]), indicating that professionals with higher technological competencies are more likely to hold favorable attitudes toward preservation. This finding resonates with the study by Akintonde and Awujoola (2022), who observed that ICT skills such as word processing and internet navigation were positively related to preservation practices, despite skill gaps in areas such as web design. Similarly, this study found that while respondents demonstrated confidence in converting hard copies to digital formats or troubleshooting software issues, they expressed weaker confidence in advanced tasks such as designing preservation programs. These results suggest that while baseline technological competence is common, advanced digital preservation skills require greater attention. The strong predictive power of technological awareness, accounting for 64% of variance in attitudes, further emphasizes that technology literacy is not only an enabler but also a determinant of professional orientation toward digital preservation. This reinforces earlier claims by Masenya and Ngulube (2020) that technological infrastructure and expertise form a core foundation of sustainable preservation models such as OAIS.

Institutional support also significantly influenced attitudes toward digital preservation, $R = .77$, $R^2 = .60$, $F(1, 43) = 63.66$, $p < .001$. The regression results indicated a positive and significant effect ($B = 0.73$, $SE = 0.09$, $\beta = .77$, $t(43) = 7.98$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.54, 0.91]), explaining nearly 60% of the variance in attitudes. This suggests that institutional resources and leadership play an essential role in shaping professional attitudes toward digital preservation. The findings are consistent with Masenya and Ngulube (2020), who noted that institutional support and management commitment were critical to sustaining digital preservation efforts. Similarly, Abubakar et al. (2024) emphasized that although staff attitudes toward preservation were generally positive, insufficient funding and neglect undermined practice. This pattern is reflected in the present study, where items such as “adequate funds for preservation activities” ($M = 3.33$, $SD = 1.41$) and “regular backup practices” ($M = 3.43$, $SD = 1.50$) received moderate ratings, suggesting gaps between awareness of importance and actual institutional practice. These findings indicate that while professionals recognize the necessity of institutional backing, they perceive deficiencies in policy enforcement and financial resources. Institutional support therefore serves as a structural condition that ensures technological skills and training can be effectively applied. Academic libraries in Pakistan, similar to those elsewhere, require stronger policy frameworks and budget allocations to reinforce positive professional attitudes toward preservation.

Professional training was also found to be a significant predictor of attitudes toward digital preservation, $R = .78$, $R^2 = .61$, $F(1, 43) = 65.78$, $p < .001$. The regression coefficient

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was positive and significant ($B = 0.72$, $SE = 0.09$, $\beta = .78$, $t(43) = 8.11$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.54, 0.89]), explaining 61% of the variance in attitudes. Respondents emphasized the importance of workshops and seminars ($M = 3.71$, $SD = 1.29$), while also noting structural gaps in formal training ($M = 3.40$, $SD = 1.21$). These results echo Sambo et al. (2017), who reported that 83% of Nigerian librarians lacked relevant training, and Sambo (2014), who found that 70% of librarians had never received preservation training. The persistent absence of structured training contributes to professional uncertainty and inconsistent practices. At the same time, the evidence from this study that training improves attitudes echoes the arguments of Gracy and Kahn (2011), who stressed that evolving professional roles require continuous education. Thus, professional training is not merely supplementary but central to shaping positive attitudes, particularly when it equips professionals with confidence in applying digital preservation tools.

A comparative assessment of the three predictors indicates that technological awareness exerted the strongest influence ($\beta = .80$, $R^2 = .64$), followed by professional training ($\beta = .78$, $R^2 = .61$) and institutional support ($\beta = .77$, $R^2 = .60$). While each of the factors significantly predicts attitudes, this ranking suggests that fostering technical competencies may have the most immediate impact. However, without institutional resources and structured training, technological awareness alone may not translate into sustainable practices. The strong correlations observed among the three factors (ranging from $r = .691$ to $r = .802$, all $p < .01$) further underscore the interplay of technology, support, and training. For instance, the correlation between professional training and technological awareness was especially strong ($r = .767$, $p < .01$), suggesting that training may act as a pathway for strengthening technological competencies. This confirms Kastlecs (2012) argument that both technical and non-technical factors shape preservation practices and supports the integrated perspective advocated by Masenya and Ngulube (2020).

The findings of this study also carry practical implications for academic libraries in Pakistan. Libraries must prioritize the development of structured training programs to ensure that technological competencies are continuously updated. Institutional support, in terms of policy formulation and funding allocation, must be strengthened to bridge the gap between awareness and practice. Furthermore, collaborative efforts across universities may help mitigate resource constraints, particularly in smaller institutions, a strategy also highlighted by Maron (2008). Theoretically, the study extends existing literature by empirically validating the role of technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training in shaping professional attitudes toward digital preservation in an underexplored context.

Conclusion

The findings of this study reveal that technological awareness, institutional support, and professional training are all significant predictors of the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation. Technological awareness emerged as the strongest predictor ($\beta = .80$, $R^2 = .64$), indicating that professionals with greater technical skills and understanding of preservation technologies are more likely to develop favorable attitudes toward digital preservation practices. Institutional support and

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professional training also showed strong positive effects, explaining 60% and 61% of the variance, respectively, which highlights their essential roles in providing the necessary resources, guidance, and continuous learning opportunities.

Overall, the results confirm that successful digital preservation in academic libraries requires a comprehensive strategy that integrates individual competencies with organizational structures and professional development opportunities. When institutions provide adequate funding, policies, and structured training, alongside fostering technological expertise, information professionals are more confident, motivated, and prepared to implement sustainable preservation practices. This integrated approach ensures that digital preservation becomes a strategic priority rather than an individual effort.

Recommendations

To develop the factors influencing the attitude of information professionals toward digital preservation at Riphah International University, here are some recommendations:

- Strengthen technological awareness through hands-on workshops and certification programs in digital preservation tools and software.
- Establish clear institutional policies and allocate dedicated budgets for digital preservation activities.
- Design structured, recurring training programs tailored to address both foundational and advanced preservation skills.
- Encourage collaborations between libraries, universities, and professional associations to share expertise and resources.
- Invest in continuous professional development through conferences, seminars, and online platforms.
- Implement monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the impact of training, institutional support, and technological awareness on digital preservation practices.

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